

MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF GROWTH AND YIELD PARAMETERS OF INDUSTRIAL SUGAR CANE IN HUMID TROPICAL AGRO-ECOLOGICAL BELT OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons at the Research Farm of Ibrahim Babangida College of Agriculture, Obubra, located in the tropical rainforest belt of Nigeria (Latitude 6°04'N, Longitude 8°21'E, and an altitude of about 1,570m above sea level). The study aimed to evaluate the morphological analysis of growth and yield parameters of industrial sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum* L.) in Nigeria's humid tropical agro-ecological belt. Twelve industrial sugarcane varieties: OG-11, B61208, AKWA-005, CO1001, KN-10, CP-65-357, OY-10, BD3745, EBON-006, HAT4, and Triton were laid out in a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. Flower initiation and arrow formation occurred in CO1001, OG-11, OY-10, CP65-357, DB3745, and AKWA-005 between 150 and 230 days after planting (DAP). AKWA-005, OY-10, DB3745, and OG-11 produced more pollen grains than CO1001 and CP65-357. A cane yield of 60.9 t/ha was obtained in CO1001, significantly higher than in EBON-006, CP65-357, and other genotypes. The Brix scale (°Bx) readings were 15.96, 16.47, and 15.32 for DB3745, B61208, and CP65-357, respectively. Similarly, indices clustered CO1001, EBON-006, DB3745, CP65-357, B61208, and AKWA-005 together. Therefore, CO1001, CP65-357, EBON-006, DB3745, B61208, and AKWA-005 are valuable for sugarcane breeding and, with their greater yield capacity, are recommended for sugarcane cultivation in the humid tropical agro-ecological zone of Nigeria.

Keywords: Growth, Yield, Industrial Sugarcane, Brix Value, Humid Tropical Belt.

INTRODUCTION

Sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum*) belongs to the grass family, Poaceae. It originated from tropical South and Southeast Asia, with different species originating in various locations, resulting in about 37 species. It is a tall perennial plant with stout, jointed, and fibrous stalks rich in sucrose. The plant can grow between 2 to 5 metres or more in length and has a high potential for biomass production. Sugarcane requires a tropical or temperate climate and typically grows to a minimum length of 2-5 metres. Approximately 195 countries grow sugarcane, producing around 1,324,000 tonnes of sugar annually. In 2008, global sugarcane production was approximately 1.5 billion tonnes, with Brazil being the largest producer in the world (Ellah *et al.*, 2017).

The plant is adaptable to most soil types and helps prevent soil erosion. It is resistant to many diseases that affect other grass species, such as maize. Sugarcane is a highly valuable crop for domestic and industrial purposes due to its nutritional and economic value. It contributes about 60% of the world's sugar supply, with Brazil, India, China, Cuba, and Mexico being the top producers (Amon *et al.*, 2020; Girel and Goroh, 2012). Sugarcane is the primary source of ethanol used by 80% of cars in Brazil, while in the United States, ethanol is mainly sourced from maize. In 2006, approximately 5.4 billion gallons of fuel were produced from sugarcane (Peacock, 2010). Additionally, sugarcane produces syrup and other substances used in medicine, pharmaceuticals, confectionery, and beverage industries.

In Africa, major sugarcane producers include Mauritius, Kenya, Sudan, Zimbabwe, Madagascar, Côte d'Ivoire, Ethiopia, Malawi, Zambia, Tanzania, Nigeria, Cameroon, and Zaire. Sugarcane was first introduced to Nigeria by European sailors in the early 15th century,

and it is now widely cultivated in various ecologies across the country. In Nigeria, sugarcane production increased from 17,200 tonnes in 1961 to 1,412,070 tonnes in 2009 (Mongaby, 2005; Ellah *et al.*, 2020). In Nigeria, sugarcane is primarily grown for sugar production and consumed domestically. Over 500,000 hectares of land are allocated for sugarcane cultivation, potentially producing over 3.0 million metric tonnes of sugar (Nicely *et al.*, 2013). The country's sugar demand is 1.45 million tonnes while refining capacity is about 2.1 million metric tonnes. Despite this excess production capacity, Nigeria imports over \$500 million of brown sugar from Brazil (Nicely *et al.*, 2013). Once a leading producer of palm oil (60% of global supply) and groundnuts (30% of global supply), Nigeria now produces only about 5% of these products (CBN, 2011; CBN, 2015). This decline has also impacted the production of other crops, including sugarcane.

The poor performance of government-owned companies compared to established private companies in Nigeria has led to serious insufficiencies in industrial sugarcane production. The sugar industry's development has been slow due to overreliance on sugar imports, and the domestic supply has not met the growing demand despite Nigeria's comparative advantages for sugarcane production (Olukunle, 2016; Dominic *et al.*, 2018).

However, sugarcane production in Nigeria and most North African countries faces significant challenges. These include poor investment and low capital outlay, lack of market networks, limited agricultural land, competition with urban needs, rising fuel prices impacting transport and production costs, and biotic and abiotic stress factors, such as infestation by cane beetles (*Migdolus fryanus*) and soft scale insects (*Pulvinaria tenuivalvata*). Additional issues include poor infrastructure for transporting harvested

cane to mills, low-skilled workforce, inadequate capacity building, absence of sugarcane growers' and technologists' associations, negative socio-economic conditions, lack of legal frameworks, and lack of national and regional networking groups. A key problem is the lack of political will to enforce strict regulations on sugar imports into the continent (Wada *et al.*, 2017).

The Cross River State has been identified as one of the Nigerian states with the potential for sugarcane cultivation (Wada *et al.*, 2017; Ellah *et al.*, 2017). In line with this, the objective of this study was to evaluate the morphological analysis of growth and yield parameters of industrial sugarcane varieties in the humid tropical agro-ecological belt of Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field trial was conducted in 2021 and 2022 at the Research Farm of Ibrahim Babangida College of Agriculture, located in the Obubra Tropical Rain Forest Belt of Nigeria. The study area is situated at Latitude 6°04'N and Longitude 8°21'E, with an altitude of about 1,570m above sea level. The experimental location is characterized by heavy annual rainfall of 2,984mm, temperatures ranging from 27 to 35°C, and relative humidity between 70% and 85%.

The soil in the area is acidic (pH 4.6 – 5.0) and low in organic matter, with total nitrogen levels between 1.0 – 1.9g/kg, available phosphorus ranging from 5.8 – 11.9mg/kg, exchangeable calcium between 0.4 – 2.8cmol/kg, and exchangeable sodium from 0.2 – 0.4cmol/kg (Amalu, 1978).

Twelve industrial sugarcane varieties (OG-11, B61208, AKWA-005, CO1001, KN-10, CP65-357, DB3745, OY-10, EBON-

006, HAT4, and TRITON) were obtained from the National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI), Badeggi, Niger State, Nigeria.

The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. The field measured 23m x 44m, and each plot measured 5m x 1.5m with an inter-row spacing of 1.5m and intra-row spacing of 1m. Planting took place in April 2021, and the cane cuttings used for planting had three nodes. The cuttings, or "setts," were 30cm long, dipped in mercurial and insecticidal solutions, drained, and then planted. Standard field maintenance practices, such as weeding, pest control, fertilizer applications, and harvesting, were carried out for both cropping seasons.

Data was collected on germination percentage (GRM) at 21 days after planting (DAP), as a percentage of cane cuttings with shoot sprouts per plot, and on establishment count (EST) at 5 months after planting (MAP). Flowering patterns were recorded from 150 to 230 days after planting, including flowering behaviour (FLB) (flowered = 1, non-flowered = 0) and flowering cycle (FCY) classified as early flowering (139-168 DAP), medium flowering (169-200 DAP), late flowering (201-245 DAP), or non-flowering. Flower emergence, arrow formation, and sexuality (SEX) (non-flowering, staminate, or female flowers) were also recorded.

Yield characteristics measured included Brix value (°Bx) using a handheld refractometer at 12 MAP, stalk length (SLNG), stalk girth (SGTH), number of millable stalks per plot (MLST), and cane yield (YLD) in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). Varieties with significantly different means were compared using Duncan's New Multiple Range Test.

Analysis of variance was carried out on pairs of variables that showed significance ($p \leq 0.05$). The generated components of the variance were used to estimate the phenotypic correlation coefficient as suggested by Singh and Chaudhary (1985): phenotypic correlation coefficient (rp) =

$$\frac{COV(C_1, C_2)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 PC1 \times \sigma^2 PC2}}$$

Where

$\sigma^2 P$ = Phenotypic variance

$COV(C_1, C_2)$ = Covariance of characters X and Y

Test of significant of correlations was done by comparing the computed values against table "t", values given by Fisher and Yates (1963).

RESULTS

The analysis of growth and yield parameters of industrial sugarcane varieties in the humid tropical agro-ecological belt of Nigeria is shown in Table 1. Germination rates across varieties ranged from 100% in C01001 and DB37/45 to slightly lower but non-significant differences in AKWA-005, B61208, OG-11, KN-10, CP65-357, EBON-006, and TRITON. The percentage of establishments mirrored this trend.

Table 1: Some growth, flowering and yield parameters of 12 industrial sugarcane varieties grown in humid tropical agro-ecology

VARIETY	GRM	EST	FLB	FCY	^o BX	SGTH	SLNG	MLST	YLD	SEX
AKWA-005	87.5 ^a	89.5 ^a	1	Early	12.9 ^e	8.2 ^{bc}	143.3 ^{ab}	6.3 ^C	38.2 ^{bc}	Male
B61208	95.4 ^a	95.5 ^a	0	NF	16.8 ^{ab}	9.2 ^a	133.8 ^b	5.1 ^e	35.5 ^{bc}	NF
OG-11	84.3 ^a	87.1 ^a	1	Medium	14.2 ^{cd}	6.7 ^d	142.1 ^b	8.1 ^b	37.1 ^{bc}	Male
C01001	100.0 ^a	95.4 ^a	1	Early	14.9 ^c	8.2 ^{bc}	153.3 ^a	7.6 ^b	60.9 ^a	Fem
KN-10	92.7 ^a	87.1 ^a	0	NF	14.4 ^{cd}	8.5 ^b	120.6 ^c	5.9 ^d	26.4 ^c	NF
CP65-357	89.9 ^a	89.9 ^a	1	Medium	15.9 ^b	7.4 ^{cd}	133.0 ^b	8.6 ^a	44.1 ^b	Fem
DB37/45	100.0 ^a	100.0 ^a	1	Early	17.4 ^a	9.3 ^a	129.7 ^{bc}	6.0 ^d	37.6 ^{bc}	Male
EBON-006	89.9 ^a	89.9 ^a	0	NF	12.8 ^e	7.8 ^{cd}	133.6 ^b	6.8 ^{bc}	48.2 ^b	NF
OY-10	64.9 ^b	67.7 ^b	1	Late	13.4 ^{de}	6.6 ^d	117.8 ^{cd}	7.0 ^{bc}	30.6 ^c	Male
HAT4	51.0 ^c	51.0 ^d	0	NF	14.5 ^{cd}	7.2 ^{cd}	101.6 ^d	4.1 ^f	9.6 ^d	NF
C00238	62.1 ^b	62.1 ^c	0	NF	13.6 ^d	7.1 ^{cd}	114.3 ^{cd}	7.4 ^b	29.2 ^c	NF
TRITON	92.8 ^a	92.8 ^a	0	NF	15.8 ^b	8.8 ^b	133.2 ^b	6.4 ^c	31.0 ^c	NF

Key: GRM = Germination Percentage, EST = Percentage of established Plants per Plot, FLB = Flowering Behavior, FCY = Flowering Cycle ^oBX = Referctomerter Brix (%). SGTH = Stalk Girth (CM), SLNG = Stalk Length (CM), MLST = Millable Stalk per plot, YLD = Cane Yield (t/ha), SEX = Sexuality, NF = Non-Flowering Fem = Female

The percentage establishment mirrored this trend. Six varieties (AKWA-005, OG-11, C01001, CP65-357, DB37/45, and OY-10) flowered in the humid environment. Varieties AKWA-005, C01001, and DB37/45 were early-flowering (135–172 DAP), OG-11 and CP65-357 were medium-flowering (169–200 DAP), while

OY-10 was late-flowering (blooming after 200 DAP).

DB37/45 had the highest Brix value of 17.0%, similar to B61208. Sucrose content ranged between 12.8% and 17.4%, which is higher than average compared to other crops. Stalk girth varied between 6.6 and 9.2 cm, with stalk lengths ranging from

101.6 to 153.3 cm at 12 months after planting. CP65-357 had the highest number of millable stalks (8.6 per plot), significantly more than the other varieties, while B61208 and HAT4 had fewer than five.

Stalk yield ranged from 9.6 t/ha in HAT4 to 60.9 t/ha in C01001, the highest yield across all varieties. EBON-006, AKWA-005, DB37/45, and OG-11 produced 48.2, 38.2, 37.6, and 37.1 t/ha, respectively.

Figure 1: Chart showing flower initiation and arrow formation in industrial sugarcane varieties in humid agro-ecological belt of Nigeria.

Male and female characterizations were based on pollen production, with AKWA-005, OG-11, DB37/45, and OY-10 identified as male due to profuse pollen production. C01001 and CP65-357 were

identified as female plants due to poor pollen production. Flower emergence occurred between 157 and 228 DAP, and arrows formed between 165 and 235 DAP (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Cluster analysis of Industrial Sugarcane Varieties

Cluster analysis using Bray-Curtis single linkage cluster analysis (BCSLCA) revealed two major clusters. OY-10 and C00238 formed one, while OG-11, AKWA-005, CP65-357, EBON-006, TRITON, B61208, DB37/45, KN-10, and C01001 formed the other, with HAT4 standing alone (Figure 2).

Table 2: K-Means clustering of the varieties

CLUSTERS	VARIETIES
1.	KN-10
2.	B61208, CP65-357, DB37/45, EBON-006, TRITON
3.	OG-11, AKWA-005
4.	C01001
5.	OY-10, HAT4, COO238

K-means clustering divided the varieties into five groups, with KN-10 in group 1, B61208, CP65-357, DB37/45, EBON-006, and TRITON in group 2, OG-11 and AKWA-005 in group 3, C01001 in group 4, and OY-10, HAT4, and C00238 in group 5 (Table 2).

Correlation Analysis

Results correlation analysis showed that most agronomic traits measured has

significant correlation with cane yield ($P < 0.05$ and 0.01) (Table 4). The cane yield among cultivators was positively correlated to Sexuality ($r = 0.50$), Germination ($r = 0.74$), % Est plant per plot ($r = 0.51$), Flowering behavior ($r = 0.59$), Stalk Weigh ($r = 0.66$) and stalk girth ($r = 0.59$) have a positive and significant correlation with cane yield.

Character	Sexuality	Germination (%)	% EST plant per Plot	Flowering Behavior	Stalk Weight (g)	Stalk Girth (Weeks)	Flowering Cycle (Weeks)	Millable Stalk Per Plot	Stalk Length (cm)	Stalk Internode Length(Cm)	^o Brix (%)	Cane Yield (t/ha)
Sexuality	1	0.74**	0.51**	0.59**	0.66**	0.59**	0.25*	0.33**	0.39**	0.30**	0.29*	0.50**
Germination		1	0.81**	0.58**	0.58**	0.60**	-0.11	0.15	0.23*	-0.17	0.15	0.63**
% EST Plant/Plot			1	0.38**	0.48**	0.44**	0.04	0.15	0.21	0.17	0.16	0.52**
Flowering Behaviour				1	0.91**	0.46**	0.15	0.10	0.17	0.28*	0.28*	0.55**
Stalk Weight (g)					1	0.55**	0.26*	0.25*	0.25*	0.46**	0.65**	0.38**
Stalk Girth						1	0.13	0.29*	0.74**	0.76**	0.97**	0.99**
Flowering Cycle (Wks)							1	0.94**	0.80**	0.43**	0.85**	0.99**
Millable Stalk/Plot								1	0.86**	0.74**	0.98**	0.95**
Stalk Length (Cm)									1	0.63**	0.85**	0.97**
Stalk Inter-Length										1	0.76**	0.48**
^o Brix (%)											1	0.22*
Cane Yield												1

Table 3: Phenotypic Correlation (r_p) for twelve morphological characteristics of Growth and yield performance of industrial sugarcane genotypes evaluated in 2021 and 2022 at Aburra humid and Tropical Rain Forest Belt of Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide important insights into the growth, flowering, and yield characteristics of industrial sugarcane varieties in the humid tropical agro-ecological belt of Nigeria. The observed variations in germination, flowering, and yield across the varieties underscore the complex interaction between genetic factors and the environment, offering key implications for sugarcane breeding and production in similar tropical climates. Sugarcane, as a C4 plant, is particularly well-suited to warm climates with adequate moisture, which aligns with the conditions found in Nigeria's humid tropics.

High germination rates observed across most varieties, particularly the 100% germination in C01001 and DB37/45, indicate that the agro-ecological conditions in this region are favorable for sugarcane establishment. While the differences in germination rates among varieties were not statistically significant, they still highlight potential variances in resilience and vigor under local environmental conditions. These results suggest that nearly all tested varieties could be viable for large-scale planting in similar tropical environments, though future studies might explore the underlying genetic traits that confer this germination success. Previous research has shown that environmental factors significantly influence germination rates, emphasizing the need for localized studies to enhance breeding programs (Lu *et al.*, (2024).

Flowering patterns classified into early, medium, and late present valuable information for breeding programs. Early-flowering varieties like AKWA-005, C01001, and DB37/45 could be particularly advantageous for breeding purposes, especially in regions where a shorter growing season is preferred. Late-flowering varieties like OY-10 offer additional opportunities for extending the

breeding window, which could be beneficial for maximizing genetic diversity in sugarcane breeding programs. These findings align with those of Imolehin and Wada (2008) and Yakubu *et al.*, (2011), although variations in sex expression (male in Ibadan and female in Bunza) indicate that environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and soil type play a role in reproductive development (Lu *et al.*, 2024; Dosso *et al.*, 2023). Such factors should be further investigated to optimize breeding strategies.

The superior yield of C01001 (60.9 t/ha), significantly higher than that of other varieties, highlights its exceptional adaptability and productivity in the humid tropical climate. This result positions C01001 as a highly promising variety for commercial cultivation, particularly in environments similar to the study location. In contrast, HAT4, which recorded the lowest yield (9.6 t/ha), might require more targeted management practices or may simply be less suited to these specific agro-ecological conditions. The variation in stalk girth, length, and number of millable stalks across varieties provides additional insights into their agronomic potential. For instance, CP65-357's highest number of millable stalks (8.6 per plot) compared to B61208 and HAT4 indicates distinct differences in their ability to produce economically viable stalks.

The high Brix value (17.0%) and sucrose content (ranging between 12.8% and 17.4%) in DB37/45 and B61208 confirm their suitability for industrial sugar production. The fact that these values exceed averages reported for other crops indicates the potential for these varieties to contribute significantly to Nigeria's sugar industry. Higher sucrose content not only enhances the economic value of the cane but also reduces processing costs per unit of sugar extracted. This aligns with findings from other studies that emphasize

the importance of selecting high-sucrose varieties for improved profitability.

The findings of this study further emphasize the sensitivity of sugarcane to environmental and climatic conditions. Growth, flowering, Brix value, and yield are all influenced by factors such as temperature, rainfall, and humidity. Recent challenges including unpredictable weather patterns due to climate change could further impact sugarcane production. Therefore, breeding programs must focus on selecting varieties that not only perform well under current climatic conditions but are also resilient to anticipated effects of global warming. This is consistent with research identifying climate as a critical determinant of sugarcane phenology and productivity.

Cluster analysis using Bray-Curtis single linkage and K-means clustering revealed clear genetic relationships among the varieties, offering valuable insights for breeding programs. The grouping of closely related varieties suggests shared genetic traits that could be exploited for breeding purposes. Understanding these genetic relationships is critical for developing new varieties that combine desirable traits such as high Brix value or improved yield. The reproductive behavior of the varieties provides important information for sugarcane breeding. Varieties producing profuse pollen could serve as male parents while those producing less pollen may be used as maternal lines. However, site-specific variation in pollen production highlights the need for localized breeding strategies that account for environmental influences on reproductive development.

The correlation between the 12 Morphological traits of growth and yield performance values was used as a basis for the identification of the Principal components (pcs) in the study. This agreed with the results of Yada et al (2010) and Budu–Apraka et al (2011). Who stated that the positive performance values are indications that they are important predictors of yield.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, regarding the cane yield, Brix value, flowering cycle, and stalk characteristics, C01001, CP65-357, EBON-006, DB37/45, B61208, and AKWA-005 are valuable materials for breeding and for consideration in sugarcane cultivation in the humid tropical agro-ecological belt of Nigeria. Due to their yield capacity and other attributes, C01001, CP65-357, EBON-006, DB37/45, B61208, and AKWA-005 are recommended for cultivation in humid and tropical agro-ecological zones in Nigeria. The traits associated with cane yields, such as sexuality, germination percentage, plant establishment per plot, flowering behaviour, stalk weight, and stalk girth, have a positive and significant correlation with cane yield. Similarly, germination percentage, establishment per plot, millable stalks per plot, stalk weight, stalk girth, stalk length, and stalk internode length are the most important characteristics for improving cane yield in sugarcane production.

REFERENCES

- Amon, T. E., Ellah, M. M., Adedzwa, D. K., Irtwange, S. V., & Ellah, J. N. (2020). Effect of nitrogen fertilizer as utilized by Bakor women farmers on the performance of sesame (*Sesame indicum*) in Ogoja LGA of Cross-River State. *Journal of Gender in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 1(1), 119-123.
- Binbol, N. L., Adebayo, A. A., & Kwon-Ndung, E. H. (2006). Influence of climatic factors on growth and yield of sugarcane in Numan, Nigeria. *Climate Research*, 32, 247-252.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2011). Integrating Nigeria's agricultural and financial value chains: The role of Nigeria incentive based risk sharing for agricultural lending (NIRSAL).
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2015). *Annual reports and statement of accounts 2015*. Abuja, Nigeria.
- Dominic, T. A., Ellah, M. M., Ellah, J. N., & Aondo, T. O. (2018). Promoting sustainable post-harvest practices of tomato through different media communication in Southern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Advances in Agricultural Research*, 8(1), 1-8.
- Dosso, S., Yoroba, F., Kouassi, B., Kouadio, K., Diawara, A., Koba, A., & Diedhiou, A. (2023). Climate impact on the productivity of sugarcane varieties in Ferkel Industrial Plantations. *Agricultural Sciences*, 14(7), 954-976.
- Ellah, M. M., Obasi, M. O., & Ellah, J. N. (2017). Comparative economic analysis of sweet potato (*Ipomoea batata* (L.) Lam) production by cooperative farmers in Vandeikya Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. *Capital Journal of Education Studies*, 5(1), 55-66.
- Ellah, M. M., Obasi, M. O., Kalu, B. A., Odiaka, N. I., & Ellah, J. N. (2020). Evaluation of food crop productivity among women farmers in Katsina-Ala Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria. *Journal of Gender in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 1(1), 24-29.
- Girel, A. A., & Giioh, D. Y. (2012). Analysis of the factors affecting sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum*) production under the out-growers scheme in Numan Local Government Area, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(8), 195-200.
- Imolehin, E. D., & Wada, A. C. (2008). Advances in sugarcane and sugar research in Nigeria. In *Training manual in sugarcane production and processing* (pp. 17-23). National Cereals Research Institute, Badegi, Niger State, Nigeria.
- Ittah, M. A., & Etefia, A. P. (2017). Flowering sexuality and yield characteristics analysis of sugarcane in tropical agro-ecology. In *Book of proceedings, 41st Annual Conference, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Nigeria*.
- Knox, J. W., Rodriguez, J. A., Nixon, D. J., & Mkhwanazi, M. (2010). A preliminary assessment of climate change impact on sugarcane in Swaziland. *Agricultural Systems*, 103, 63-72.
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- Lu, G., Liu, P., Wu, Q., Zhang, S., Zhao, P., Zhang, Y., & Que, Y. (2024). Sugarcane breeding: a fantastic past and promising future driven by technology and methods. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 15, 1375934.
- National Cereals Research Institute. (2012). Identifying suitable sites for sugarcane hybridization and fuzzi raising in Nigeria project: A logbook. Badeggi, Nigeria.
- Nicely, R., Nzeka, U., & Olaito, P. (2013). Annual sugar report for Nigeria 2013. *Global Agricultural Information Network (GAIN) Report*, USDA Foreign Agricultural Services, 16-20.
- Olukunle, O. T. (2016). Economic analysis of profitability and competitiveness of sugarcane enterprise in Nigeria. *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*, 8(6), 160-171.
- Peacock, K. W. (2010). Biotechnology and genetic engineering. In *Global issues* (pp. 366-369). Infobase Publishing.
- Srivastava, A. K., & Rai, M. K. (2012). Sugarcane production: Impact of climate change and its mitigation. *Biodiversitas*, 13(4), 214-227.
- Udoimuk, A. B. B., Osang, J. E. A., Ettah, E. B. A., Ushie, P. O. A., Egor, A. O. A., & Alozie, S. I. (2014). An empirical study of seasonal rainfall effect in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Applied Physics*, 5(5), 7-15.
- Wada, A. C., Abo-Elwafa, A., Salaudeen, M. T., Bello, L. Y., & Kwon-Ndung, E. H. (2017). Sugarcane production problems in Nigeria and some Northern African countries. *Direct Research Journal of Agriculture and Food Science*, 5(3), 141-160.
- Yakubu, A. A., Ango, & Bunza, N. A. (2011). Sugarcane marketing options for sustainable agricultural development in Bunza Local Government Area of Kebbi State, Nigeria. 76-80.
- Zhao, D., & Li, Y. R. (2015). Climate change and sugarcane production: potential impact and mitigation strategies. *International Journal of Agronomy*, 2015(1), 547386.
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